

tribolium confusum:strain bII



tribolium confusum:strain bIII



tribolium confusum:strain bIV



Tribolium confusum:4 grams of flour



*Tribolium confusum*: 8 grams of flour



Tribolium confusum:16 grams of flour



Tribolium confusum:32 grams of flour



*Tribolium confusum*:64 grams of flour



Tribolium confusum:128 grams of flour



Tribolium confusum:no



Tribolium confusum:1



*Tribolium confusum*:2



*Tribolium confusum*:3



*Tribolium castaneum*:1



*Tribolium castaneum*:2



*Tribolium castaneum*:3



*Tribolium castaneum*:4



*Tribolium castaneum*:5



*Tribolium castaneum*:6



*Tribolium castaneum*:7



*Tribolium castaneum*:8



*Tribolium castaneum*:9



*Tribolium castaneum*:10

